

Designing and Printing a Custom Memory Book Cover

Memories are some of the most treasured non-tangible assets in our lives. They derive their value from the fact that the events from which the memories were created cannot be brought to life again, thanks to passage of time. Such events can only be recreated in the mind. Luckily, a [memory book](#) can serve as a subtle way of preserving some of the most memorable moments in life. Such treasures can be made more vivid through a professionally designed memory book cover.

How important is such a book's cover?

We have been taught not to judge a book by its cover. However, this has often been critiqued as an excuse to either play down people's creativity in cover design, and to not ignore sloppy works of art in the hope that we will find something of value inside. Whichever way you look at it, an impressive memory book cover would be something anyone would like to see more of. Such a cover will also be inviting to your guests to delve into important events in your life.

Can anyone make his or her own cover?

About two decades ago, memory book cover design was an exclusive reserve for professional printers. But that has changed now, with technology becoming more affordable to the masses. Today you can design your own beautiful cover using specialized design software and print the artwork right at home. However, some people might need assistance in creating such designs, either for lack of design skills, or for want of more professional looking designs. For such people, professional designers using specialized tools come in handy.

What options does one have in designing and printing the covers?

When you decide you need a great looking cover, there are two major options. You might wish to outsource the entire process to a professional design studio, or you might outsource just a part of the process which might be beyond your capabilities. For instance, you might opt to select and submit images that you wish to have printed on the cover, or you might download cover design software to your computer and assemble the images yourself. Once through, you may upload and send the design works to the printer. The printer, on his part, will take the work through the professional printing process and send you the final output to your preferred address.

What other considerations should I make in the design process?

There is a myriad of factors to consider in the process, key among them being cover type, dimensions and type of binding. To start with, you might choose a pre-designed cover that the printer may choose for you, or you may opt for a custom one. Already designed covers usually cost less than your custom designed ones, for the simple reason that the initial design and production costs will probably have already been met. This is as opposed to custom designed covers where you will have to meet the design and production costs. You also want to be sure that the cover will fit the book, so you need to take proper dimensions. Two common dimensions are 5.5" x 4.25", as well as 7" X 9", but you can work with the size that serves your purposes. As for the type of binding, Smyth-sewn and case binding come in handy for works not exceeding 40 and 30 pages respectively. Saddle stitch would work well for soft cover

books not exceeding 80 pages, while perfect binding would be a good option for hard cover jobs in excess of 80 pages. However, a most common type of binding for memory books is spiral binding.

What aesthetics can one add to the cover?

While it is common to find memory books with just a cover whose main purpose is protecting the inside pages from the weather, much can be done to enhance the book's aesthetic value. A common way is by adding a glossy shin to the cover. Besides making the cover waterproof, the coating brings with it a feel of refinement. Another common beauty technique is embossing of the printed surface. This involves coating the imprints and images with a special heat-sensitive chemical, and then passing the art work through a special heating machine. Through this treatment, specific areas on the cover get a textural appeal that can be felt through touch.

There is much that one can do to create a great looking memory book cover. This is more so given the availability of design software that one can download and use at home. With greater accessibility of high quality [term paper help](#) and printing technologies, the cost of designing and producing covers has come down, too. If you are developing such covers for a homeschool, you can be certain that the memories recorded in the books will remain a treasure too in the minds of your students as they grow up.